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Evaluation of Greek Second Chance Schools in Prison by Detainees

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Abstract

With the establishment of Second Chance Schools (SCS) inside Greek prisons, a more systematic and integrated effort was made for the overall development of trainees. Many studies have been conducted regarding the work that SCS provide. For this reason, a systematic review of the relevant bibliography and a compilation of the findings of the studies realized between 2006-2018, regarding the evaluation of the educational program provided by SCS in the prison, was considered appropriate. The results demonstrate that all inmate trainees evaluate SCS positively, concerning the educators, the school climate, the curriculum that incorporates subjects that cater for their educational needs, the active teaching techniques and flexibility in syllabus. On the other hand, trainee inmates make negative judgments about the organizational part mainly, while in the curriculum they point out some failures and deficiencies, especially in relation to their future professional reintegration.

Keywords: Correctional Adult Education, Second Chance Schools, Evaluation

Introduction

The operation of Second Chance Schools for Adults in Prisons (SCS) is an important development, as their curriculum is based on the principles of adult education and contributes to raising the level of education of detainees.

The present research is a systematic review in the field of correctional education in Greece, with the aim of gathering the findings of studies that investigated the views and judgments of detainees on the provided training program of SCS. Altogether, nineteen (19) investigations have emerged from our search for this particular issue. We first outline the theoretical framework of the analysis with reference to the training provided in the SCS (curriculum and institutional framework) and the perceptions -positive and negative- of the SCS trainees and then present the methodology, results and conclusions.

1. SCS in Greece

In November 1995, the European Commission's White Paper for the first time referred to the proposal to implement a program called Second Chance School. This is how the European Association of Cities, Schools and Second Chance Schools was created in 1999. The main objective of SCS is to reduce inequalities and to combat

social and economic exclusion through education. The White Paper (1995) does not refer to inmates as a target group of SCS, but has all the characteristics of a target group of SCS, as they "have a low level of education and are de facto included in those not only at risk but experiencing marginalization and exclusion" (Vergidis, Asimaki & Tzintzidis, 2007, p. 70).

Consequently, the choice of the Greek State to establish SCS in prisons, according to the corresponding European Action Plan, clearly demonstrates the need to provide integrated education to detainees, with a view to the overall development of trainees and their better participation in economic, social and cultural events, as well as their more effective participation in the workplace. They are institutional social justice and encourage a second chance for detainees to make a fresh start, change their way of thinking and acting, and set a new course in their lives by making the right choices.

The training provided in the SCS is systematic and continuous and leads to the acquisition of a degree equivalent to the Gymnasium certificate. The total duration of the course is 18 months, namely two training years with a 25-hour weekly program. The weekly program is divided mainly as follows: 20 hours for the above Grades, 3 hours for projects and 2 hours for consulting services.

It is noted that SCS operate with curricula that are "open and flexible, resulting from the diagnosis of knowledge needs and skills of trainees" (MR1861 / 08-07-2014, vol. B). Thus, the program can be modified according to the specific educational needs that will arise and the priorities to be set (MR1861 / 08-07-2014, vol. B).

The cornerstone of the education offered is a multilingual network aiming at the acquisition of modern knowledge, skills and attitudes that will help learners in social, economic integration and development and includes Greek and English Linguistic Literacy, Numerical, Computer, Environmental, Scientific, Social and Aesthetic Literacy (Hondolidou, 2003).

• **Linguistic Literacy**

Greek

The goal is for each trainee to be able to handle written and oral speech better. This is achieved through interesting and constructive methods, such as dealing with texts and types of speech selected from a wide range of media and cultural sources.

English

English is a prerequisite in the professional field. The purpose of this Literacy is to enable learners to make effective use of English in real-world situations using modern learning methods and combining other literacy skills such as IT.

• **Numeric Literacy**

Particular emphasis is placed on the practical application of mathematics to the everyday life of the learners.

• **Computer Literacy**

Computer use is a prerequisite almost everywhere in the workplace and in public announcements. Trainees get in touch with the computer and its core programs. In fact, they have the opportunity to become certified and thus obtain a valuable qualification for their professional rehabilitation.

• **Environmental Literacy**

The aim is to inform the environmental issues first and to activate the learners thereafter by taking part in actions aimed at environmental protection.

• Scientific Literacy

Physics courses are conducted combining theory with practice (laboratory experiments).

• Social Literacy

It aims to meet the needs of trainees in understanding social phenomena in contemporary multicultural contexts, in activating trainees as citizens by taking active initiatives to address issues of concern to society as a whole. The already existing experiences and fragmented knowledge of the trainees are constituted on a theoretical basis.

• Aesthetic Literacy

It aims at connecting the learners with the arts and showcasing their artistic skills, revealing their creative part.

They are also provided with Vocational Guidance Trainees by the Vocational Guidance Counselor and psychological support by the Psychologist Counselor. This is an innovation that fully agrees with the general philosophy and purpose of SCS. Both of these specialties have an important role to play in helping trainees overcome difficulties along the way, as well as helping them gain confidence and professional ability to improve their lives.

The educators who teach at SCS are mainly permanent educators of Secondary Education with transference to these special schools. The selection criteria are set by INEDIVIM with a special accretion and preference to those with postgraduate and adult education and previous experience in adult education.

As far as trainee assessment is concerned, it is descriptive and focuses on reflecting knowledge and skills in all literacy but also on school activities eg workshops or action plans, synthetic work, material dossiers, highlighting areas to be improved (MR 1861/08-07-2014, No. B). According to Katsarou (2010) "the learner's progress is not compared to that of the rest, but the focus is on his individual progress" (p. 47). The SCS curriculum, taking into account the contemporary demands of literacy and wanting individuals to participate actively in the ever-changing conditions of society, goes beyond static linguistic and numerical knowledge to a more general attempt to acquire new skills through experiential learning and learning techniques, building up new knowledge. The student is regarded not as a receiver but as a constructor or producer of knowledge, since the end product reflects and actually extends his / her personal experience, commitment and expectations (Leadbetter 2004; European Association for Adult Education 2006). It is, therefore, a curriculum that is merged with flexibility and classification. This means that the organization of space, control, planning, rhythm, intensification, duration of each activity are at the discretion of instructor and trainee, and on the other hand the courses are not confined to the boundaries of their respective discipline (Bernstein, 1991, pp. 67-69). In summary, SCSs aim to provide trainees with knowledge that will prove useful and necessary both for their professional and socio-political development and for the overall development of their personality.

2. SCS in Greek prisons

With this in mind, in 2004, the innovative SCS institution was introduced in prisons in Greece and operated the first school in the Larissa Prison. Since 2005, SCS has established several prisons in the country: Korydallos Attikis, Grevena, Trikala, Nigrita Serres, Diavata Thessaloniki, Patra, Eleonas Thebes, Domokos Fthiotida, Malandrino Fokidas and Agia (Chania, Crete).

The White Paper (1995) does not refer to inmates as a target group of SCS, but has all the characteristics of a target group of SCS, as they "have a low level of education and are de facto included in those not only at risk but experiencing marginalization and exclusion" (Vergidis, Asimaki & Tzintzidis, 2007, p. 70).

Consequently, the choice of the Greek State to establish SCS in prisons, according to the corresponding European Action Plan, clearly demonstrates the need to provide integrated education to detainees, with a view to the overall development of trainees and their better participation in economic, social and cultural events, as well as their more effective participation in the workplace. They are institutional social justice and encourage a second chance for detainees to make a fresh start, change their way of thinking and acting, and set a new course in their lives by making the right choices.

3. Trainees' perceptions of SCS

Several studies have been conducted that relate to trainees' perceptions of the SCS they are attending, the findings of which are interesting, as both positive and negative SCS issues arise. Sometimes there are contradictory perceptions, as not all learners perceive and evaluate data in the same way.

3.1. Positive perceptions of SCS trainees

In previous empirical research (Alexopoulou, 2006, p. 75; Ananiadis, 2007, p. 38; Landritsis, 2007, p. 111) on various SCSs on learners' perceptions, trainees record mentality and SCS operate. The positive perceptions also include length of time (Landritsch, 2007, p. 85), timetable (Lazu, 2008, p. 56), lack of evaluation (Landritsch, 2007, pp. 91-92) and additional advisory services (Alexopoulou, 2006, p. 96), but also laboratories and action plans (Ananiadis, 2007, p. 38). In addition, educators' contribution to both the pedagogical climate and the way they teach is generally viewed as positive (Landritsch, 2007, p. 86). They also state that everyone learns what they really need, in a climate of free expression and acceptance, in pleasant ways (Aleksopoulou, 2006, p. 96), thus demonstrating that learners prefer free dialogue and open communication, in contrast with their teacher's monologue that is repulsive (Kokkos, 2005, pp. 88-89).

3.2. Negative and contradictory perceptions of SCS trainees

SCS trainees negatively evaluate building facilities and their spatial distribution, SCS organization, teaching hours, lack of evaluation, length of time and additional services. Also, some are not satisfied with the logistical infrastructure (Vergidis, 2003, pp. 126- 127; Landritsis, 2007, p. 86). Regarding the non-use of textbooks, the majority of them are satisfied with that since they would not have time to read the books at home (Lazou, 2008, p. 56), although there are always students who want the textbook. Negative perceptions are also expressed about their heterogeneity (mainly at the educational level), the cost of commuting, as well as the behavior of their 'classmates' (Vergidis, 2003, pp. 126- 127; Landritsis, 2007, p. 90). Regarding literacy, they find them interesting (Ananiadis, 2007, p. 38; Lazou, 2008, p. 56). Of course there are trainees who complain about the low level in the class. However, on several issues the views of the trainees are contradictory, such as lack of assessment, duration of study, teaching hours, teaching materials and action plans, as some judge them positively and others negatively. In conclusion, the trainees' image of SCS is positive. However, a particular group of trainees studying in SCS, who are still in prisons, inevitably exhibits significant differences from the trainees of the other SCS, but at the same time, as the results of the present study will show, their perceptions for the training provided by SCS are largely identical to those of trainees outside prison. In some cases, their perceptions are much more positive and this can be interpreted as a result of the benefits of escaping from pains of imprisonment.

4. Methodology of the research

The present work is a systematic review in the field of prison education. According to the manuals for researchers by the Cochrane (2015) and Cambell (2014) organizations, in order for a review to be considered systematic, it should satisfy some principles when designing and implementing it. In brief, we present the principles of the methodological steps of the research process in the systematic review, which were followed in this study:

- Formulation of the research question. Our research question was: What are the trainee inmates' motivation for taking part in educational programs?
- Defining the criteria for searching and selecting the material to be studied Defining the criteria for the inclusion and exclusion of primary studies.
- Thorough search and identification of the studies to be included in the analysis based on the research question.

- Full and detailed report on the material and methods of collecting and analyzing both quantitative and qualitative data.
- Synthesis of the results.

4.1. Purpose

The purpose of this review is to synthesize data from individual investigations into the evaluation of SCS detainees' training program provided in prison.

4.2. Research question

The research question was:

How do trainee detainees evaluate the SCS training program provided?

4.3. Search method

Initially, a search for sources of material collection was conducted. Since this systematic review concerns the training of adult inmates in Greece, we searched in national databases and search engines, article references, abstracts of papers in conference proceedings, databases of doctoral and postgraduate dissertations. More specifically, Google Scholar, online libraries of Greek universities - including the Hellenic Open University - and the National Documentation Center were used. In cases where the material was not available electronically with open access, the file was searched for in the libraries' premises or the full text order service was used wherever possible. Also, articles published in scientific journals, such as "Adult Education", the "Aretha" Scientific Yearbook, or on scientific websites such as the Adult Education Network of Crete have been searched for. Finally, there was a personal communication with a researcher to locate research that could not be retrieved in any other way.

The systematic review was conducted between 20th April 2019 and 10th June 2019. The search resulted in 44 titles in Greek (3 doctoral theses, 37 postgraduate dissertations and 4 articles). At the initial screening, 41 of them were identified as potentially relevant, requiring a full text review in order to select the review studies. After being studied systematically, the researches which converged on the research question were selected. Thus, we resulted in 19 studies, which had been evaluated in the SCS in prison training program.

4.4 Data recording and analysis

Evaluation of the studies included in this systematic review was difficult, as quantitative and qualitative studies as well as mixed methodology studies were identified. Therefore, their quality could not be assessed on the basis of a published evaluation tool. However, their methodology was tested (relevance of research questions and results, sample, data collection research tool and data analysis techniques).

Key elements of the identity of the analyzed researches are illustrated in the following Table:

Table 1. The identity of the researches

Author	Time	Place	Sample	Methodology
Papadaki	2006	Women's Prison of Korydallos	10M	Qualitative
Vergidis, Asimaki Tzintzidis	2007	Korydallos SCS	76 (43M-33F)	Quantitative
Gravalou	2010	Larissa SCS	32M (10/22)	Qualitative and Quantitative
Papathanasiou, N.	2010	Judicial Prison of Diavata	52M	Quantitative
Iliopoulou	2011	Domokos SCS and Eleonas SCS	16 (8M- 8F)	Qualitative
Kouimtzi	2011	3 rd SCS of Thessaloniki	11M	Qualitative
Panteleri	2014	Diavata SCS	10M	Qualitative

Papathanasiou, H.	2014	Larissa SCS	83 M(80/3)	Quantitative and qualitative
Papaioannou	2015	Korydallos SCS	18M	Qualitative
Chrysikopoulou	2015	Women's Prison of Elaiona	20F	Quantitative
Sakka	2015	Korydallos SCS	7M	Qualitative
Korella	2016	Grevena SCS	14F	Qualitative
Mparpakos	2016	Korydallos SCS and Grevena SCS	32M (16+16)	Qualitative
Touloumi	2016	Elaionas SCS	15F	Qualitative
Vergopoulou	2017	Elaionas SCS	20F	Qualitative
Kofini	2017	3 rd SCS of Thessaloniki	10M	Qualitative
Drillia	2018	Korydallos SCS	77M	Quantitative and qualitative
Papadionysiou	2018	Elaionas SCS	9F	Qualitative
Stergiou	2018	Judicial Prison of Chania	10M	Qualitative

Note: M= Men, F= Female

The total sample of systematic review trainees is 522 detainees, of which 403 are men and 119 are women. Of the 19 surveys, 13 were developed by qualitative methodology, 3 by quantitative and 3 by mixed (quantitative and qualitative).

After collecting the data we proceeded with the content analysis as it is "a technique used for objective, systematic and quantitative description of the content in written or oral communication" (Filiass, 2001, 196). It is a process consisting of systematically measuring units of the material under investigation, according to categories formulated by the researcher (Kyriazis, 2002, p. 299). In this case, the categories were formed during the examination of the material, which were finalized through the continuous interplay of theory and data. Based on the methodology described above, the results are listed in the next section.

5. Results

The total number of studies, including evaluations by the trainees themselves of the training program provided by SCS in prisons, is 19: (Papadaki, 2006; Vergidis, Asimaki Tzintzidis, 2007; Gravalou, 2010; Papathanasiou, 2010; Kouimtzis, 2011; Pantelleri, 2014; Papathanassiou, 2014; Papaioannou, 2015; Sakka, 2015; Chrysikopoulou, 2015; Korella, 2016; Mparpakos, 2016; Touloumi, 2016; Vergopoulou, 2017; Kofini, 2017; Drillia, 2018; Papadionysiou, 2018; Stergiou, 2018) and the whole sample of research trainees comprises 506 detainees. Here are the results:

Papadaki (2006) finds that prisoner trainees are satisfied with their attendance at the prison SCS, as they value educational programs aimed at completing a degree (basic) and must continue in this direction - providing interpretation of the positive evaluation by trainees, the researcher puts forward the view that "these programs play the role of making up for the lost time, the time during which the academic education of these women should have been completed." Also, all detainees praise their educators, who create a positive atmosphere in the classroom by showing understanding and offering help while they consider that their choice of this responsible and sensitive post was absolutely right since they have the suitable qualifications. Of course, there are also problems: Half of the inmates refer to deficiencies in the poor facilities and equipment of the classrooms with modern facilities, as well as in the learning material that they must have in order to successfully attend classes. They believe that vocational training programs need a radical change in their targeting, how they are implemented and how they relate to assisted resettlement and rehabilitation institutions.

In Vergidis, Asimaki Tzintzidis study (2007), the positive and negative aspects of the SCS are studied by the sample learners. Positive recordings in women reach 100%, while in males are also very high i.e. 88.9%. Few samples of the positive comments: "... School is a Godsend gift. There are only positive things about school ... ", "Positive aspects: Too many and indescribable ", "Negative aspects, I can't say they exist in school. Of course, there are shortcomings ... ".

In Gravallo (2010) research, which examined the inmates' views on the technical teachings used in all literacy, they rated them very positive as they became active members rather than passive recipients of knowledge. They were given a "voice", as they typically say. The contribution of teaching techniques is great, according to the recordings, in acquiring knowledge, increasing their interest in learning, communicating with their educators, a little less in working with their classmates (this is attributed to the conflicts within in prison with their detainees), in developing their critical thinking. At the same time, they are given the opportunity to exchange views, to analyze situations, to discover reality and to try giving solutions to various issues themselves. Inmate trainees also find that the modules are tailored to their own needs and interests, commenting that this helps them to speak their mind freely and take initiatives, situations that are unprecedented in prison circumstances, as they "show respect for their views, enabling them to talk about their problems, the problems of their work, their society and the world at large."

Papathanasiou (2010) raises questions about space and time of study in his research. A large percentage of trainees (63.5%) say they are satisfied with the study area (they mean their cells), while study time is characterized by 71.1%. The school climate was assessed as positive by the students (78.9%) and students were asked to rate the SCS educators. Their answers show that a strong majority of about 79% of the respondents find the educators positive or very positive. And the majority of teaching materials (books, maps, projectors, notebooks, pencils, etc.) are considered them to be quite appropriate (82.6%). Trainees also appreciate the lack of textbooks and the non-mandatory coverage of specific curricula. Regarding the suitability of the library and computers, the positive responses also outperform (82.6% and 82.3% respectively).

The sample of trainee detainees in Iliopoulou's survey (2011) only positively judged: "... I understand them here (in prison) and have a question I will have to find the teacher and explain, while this was not the case. Everything is understandable here", "... yes ... it met my expectations quite a bit", "... The school is happy for me no", "... I was afraid that inmates would create havoc, as is the case generally in cells. Here we help each other, we work together, we are a team, whereas in prison we are not like that". One prisoner is trying to interpret why they all look good in prison school: "... when you leave the cell, the closure they have inside you, everything looks good to you". They also make positive judgments about their educators - a typical quote: "I didn't expect the educators to be so nice and kind to us!" However, they seem to be concerned with the daily physical examinations carried out by the store staff both on their way to and from school, without being a hindrance to the desire to study.

Inmate trainees in the study of Kouimtzi (2011) say that the school environment is very pleasant and has nothing to do with the prison environment. In their view, the classrooms are much better than those of regular schools. It is also generally accepted that educators are extremely capable, they show them understanding during the lesson, provide valuable assistance when they face small-scale difficulties and they treat them nicely. There are similar findings to Panteleri's research (2014), as the sample responded only with praiseworthy comments on the SCS and hardly reported anything negative. They list important benefits they have gained from their studies, such as knowledge, skills, adopting a healthy attitude towards life, and report the lack of text books as the only negative aspect. Some of the answers are as follows: "The school has only good things ... It opened my mind ... It taught me to behave in a team ...", "it liberated me", "the only negative thing is that we haven't got textbooks and we use photocopies instead...".

The sample of inmates trained in the Papathanasiou study (2014), evaluating the facilities and the interior of the school, rated them as 100% satisfactory. Also, the level of satisfaction with the attitude and behavior of the headmaster is high (74%). Exactly the same level of satisfaction is recorded for educators. On a more specific question, they rate the teaching method very positively (80%). The evaluation of the services of the vocational guidance counselor is also interesting: 50% of the sample evaluate them negatively. Also, investigating the most

important problems faced by research students during their two-year schooling highlights issues such as difficulty communicating with foreigners, lack of heating and internet, and the early waking up (25%). In addition, an existing problem recorded by 25% of the sample is the delayed in school staffing, a problem that concerns all SCSs and not just this one. Overall, however, school satisfaction is high (ranging from pretty much to very 100%).

In Papaioannou's survey (2015), when inmates were asked to suggest improvements to the existing SCS program, 50% stated that it did not need improvement, thus indicating their satisfaction. The climate assessment in the classroom was very positive and 78% attributed it to the contribution of the educators. They also rate the educators (100%) positively on both the educational approach and the attitude they have towards them. Typical recording: "They're perfect. I have changed 10 schools and, I am fully aware, for the first time, that they are perfect".

In Chrysikopoulou study (2015), trainees evaluating instructional techniques find that they learn better with active techniques, yet educators use more traditional methods, resulting in boredom and poorer performance in lessons. The researcher finds that many questions have contradictory answers, more specifically, when using the interview method, trainees express negative evaluations, when filling in the questionnaire their evaluations are much more positive. However, according to the researcher, this is because they do not really evaluate the teaching techniques but the SCS itself and how it works, as they believe that the school has a lot to offer them both at the level of learning and at the level of self-improvement. Evaluating teaching techniques in relation to assisting in communicating with the educators, the positive responses reach 100%, while in the fellow detainees it reaches 50%, which if interpreted, is the existing relationships among them. They also evaluate techniques positively, no matter whether they are active or traditional, in developing critical thinking and social reflection.

Several problems are observed by trainees in Sakka's study (2015), which mainly concern facilities and organizational issues. Specifically, they complain about building facilities and lack of equipment, delay in employment of teaching staff, but also of the problematic procedure of borrowing books from the school library because of the way the prison operates and its regulations.

The quality of educational programs is judged by the trainees to be satisfactory, in Korella's study (2016), which focuses their positive comments on the impact of the learning process on their way of thinking and shaping their character. However, some inadequacies are also found. When students talk about their educators, they are very pleased with the educators' attitude towards them and the respect they receive by them. In Barbako's research (2016), trainees positively evaluate the SCS curriculum as they all refer to positive changes in themselves and focus on the improvement in their knowledge, attitudes and behaviors. When referring to difficulties they face while studying, they point out the important help of their educators in dealing with difficulties. The sample of female trainees in Vergopoulou's research (2017) positively assesses their education on their personal development - cognitive development, psycho-mental development, moral strengthening - and the treatment of the pains of imprisonment to a great extent. However, they appreciate to a smaller degree about the dynamics of the educational process in their vocational rehabilitation, as they consider that the education they attended was of limited or insignificant importance for their professional integration or reintegration as it did not offer any specialization in occupations they would like to pursue after their incarceration or in other objects in demand in the professional arena. Also, another comment refers to the responsible authorities which did not take into account the educational and professional background of those who expressed an interest in training, and to the fact that all detainees have not the same opportunities in education. However, the contribution of education is mentioned by trainees as important to the activation and development of their social inclinations and skills.

Kofini (2017) states that the students who participated in her research respect and love the school and state it in many ways: they come on time to the lesson, they usually show diligence, consistency and willingness to cooperate in the classroom. They consider their teachers' contribution to the learning process and the difficulties they face as positive. But they also mention some inhibiting factors, such as banning the use of the Internet for educational purposes, which greatly limits the ability to search for information and ultimately disadvantages the learning process, as well as tight school hours which limit study time.

In Drillia's study (2018) trainees were asked to evaluate the positive and negative elements of their attendance at the prison SCS. Admittedly, the trainees state that the school can only have a positive impact on their lives and do not report any negative elements. The new knowledge, in their view, is the most positive element, along with the positive change in the level of their psychology, adding to the contribution of educators to this change. However, they find it problematic that not all detainees have the opportunity to study at SCS and that there is a shortage of educators. Moreover, they find it difficult to keep up with school hours and especially morning waking due to poor living conditions in confinement. Negative reference is made by trainees to the SCS process: sometimes difficulties arise, mainly of a bureaucratic nature, in addition convicts are allowed to study only by exception, and may be prevented from attending school by the prosecutor for penal or behavioral reasons.

The trainees in Papadionysiou's study (2018) positively evaluate both the SCS lessons, which they find very interesting, and the learning climate that is shaped in the classroom, in which they feel pleasure, calmness, freedom, serenity, compassion, animation and respect.

All trainees in Stergiou's research (2018) have a positive view of existing prison education and training programs, as they escape the monotonous prison environment, have the opportunity to creatively use their dead-free time and open perspectives to improve their daily lives in prison. A very typical quote from a trainee: "It's like asking a blind man if he wants light, so is it for us, we want programs, programs, whatever happens helps us and is for our good." However, they point out that the fact that learning is strictly limited within a specific time frame in the prison program works negatively and thus they miss the opportunity to broaden their level of knowledge and make creative use of their free time.

The positive aspects of SCS education are mentioned by most detainees, as well as the lack of school textbooks and the lack of specific teaching material. It is clear that the curriculum has taken into account both the need for active involvement of learners and the discovery, experiential and dynamic learning, developing metacognitive skills, accomplished "through an open framework that allows goals to be constantly redefined, content modified to suit learners' needs, and methods to be changed accordingly ..." (Anagnou and Nikolopoulou, 2007). However, there are conflicting views on the same issue, as the book for many detainees identifies with school, due to their prior experience in formal education.

In all surveys trainees reported acquiring knowledge, skills and adopting a healthy attitude through in-prison training. Many studies confirm the above finding: Muñoz (2009) points out that prisons should be designed for positive change and human development. Welch (1996) argues that prison education programs continue to draw citizens' support because, in essence, education itself is positively valued in our society. Lejins (1971) writes: "Since education is a good indication of the likelihood of a person's success in modern society, it seems necessary to improve prison training programs so that [detainees] acquire the academic skills necessary to have a realistic second chance to become creative members of community life" (p.26). As reported by Eikeland, Manger and Asbjørnsen (2009, p. 11), education helps to instill in the trainee the feeling that they remain part of the wider community and remind them that they will be members of society after their release. According to Putnam (2000), education and vocational training help develop social capital. Also, through participation in educational programs, the inmates strengthen their self-esteem, improve their social skills (Parker, 1990) and feel content, because they are given the opportunity to highlight the positive aspects of their personality (Kett, 1995). A recent systematic review of all the research done in Greece on the value of education (Papaioannou and Anagnou, 2019) also confirms the value of correctional education at multiple levels.

In addition, the view of trainee detainees about their educators is very positive. A study conducted by Breggins and Talbot (2003) in 10 prison training groups in the United Kingdom confirms the inmates' support by educators in learning difficulties. In another survey conducted in Greece (Papaioannou, Anagnou, Vergidis, 2016) the opinions of the trainees show a very positive assessment of the educators' work, in terms of the educational approach, the attitude they adopt and their overall behavior. Also, very positive points are their involvement in shaping a good and collaborative climate within the learning-friendly classroom, which is also highlighted in the present study. It is also reported that educators make a decisive contribution to inmates overcoming their learning difficulties –caused by their previous deficit education- with the use of a differentiated pedagogical approach and

counseling that focuses on individual needs, interests and abilities. In particular, the techniques applied during the teaching process are one of the most important issues (Courau, 2000; Noyé & Piveteau, 1999; Brookfield, 1996; Rogers, 1999; Vaikousi et al., 1999; Kokkos, 2005, 1999), because they are directly related to the effectiveness of learning (Rogers, 1999; Kokkos, 1999) and their proper selection by the educator enhances the participants' active participation and self-determination. In order for education to be beneficial and effective, it must on the one hand respond to the needs of detainees, and on the other, ensure the continuity of the learning process as well as the possibility of the participation of all detainees, with the basic, of course, condition that the difficulties that arise in prison at the same time be addressed (Dimitrouli et al., 2006).

On the other hand, trainee detainees evaluate negatively some issues that are mainly related to organizing. In particular, they consider the lack of facilities unacceptable, a problem that concerns the whole school community in Greece, as well as the delay in staffing the school with educational staff. The bureaucratic difficulties of attending SCS are also negative, with the result that not all detainees have the opportunity to receive education. In addition, lack of personal study space is considered a problem. However, it is a given that the nature and function of the prison as well as the conditions there, such as overcrowding and improper cell configuration, make it difficult to have a personal space.

Trainee detainees raise three more important issues: 1. The use of traditional teaching methods by some educators that results in lesser effectiveness in the lessons, compared to other courses in which educators use active teaching techniques. The interpretation that can be given is that many educators in prison schools did not intend to teach in this area. Without training they are forced to use their intuition and do not have the skills needed to understand and manage their new experience (Papaioannou, Anagnou, Vergidis, 2016). 2. The lack of adequate guidance services. This is a serious issue, because Career Counseling plays a crucial role in reducing relapse as it is built around the concept of work and is considered a criminal preventive tool. Downes (1998, p.6) has shown that unemployment rates have an indirect and predominantly complex effect on crime rates. Detainees are demanding more time by the vocational guidance counselor, more information, establishing contacts with prospective employers and post-release support. 3. Lack of specialization and focus on professional arena. The professional rehabilitation of detainees is of great importance, because it reduces the recidivism and offers a smooth social reintegration and removal of the prisoner's position. Therefore, the curriculum must also have this orientation, without neglecting the value of providing holistic education aimed at the overall development of detainees. As Cosman (1995, p. 73) states, when prison education is limited to the basic levels of training and development of basic life skills, the path of human development does not go far. It is clear that positive evaluation outweighs the negative quality of education content and the short- and long-term benefits for trainee detainees.

Conclusions

The general finding from the study of all surveys is that the training provided to SCS has many advantages, while the negative comments are much less and mainly related to the facilities and organizing, but also to some extent to the content of the curriculum. All inmates trainees evaluate SCS positively, because they only benefit from studying there. Previous research-review (Papaioannou, Anagnou, 2019), which examined the benefits to detainees attending prison schools, confirms the positive assessment. Other positive comments involve educators who encourage them, positive school climate, curriculum that incorporates subjects that cater for the educational needs of detainees, active teaching techniques and flexibility in syllabus related to their not using textbooks. On the other hand, trainee inmates make negative judgments about the organizational part (lack of facilities, delay in school staffing, bureaucratic difficulties) fact that impedes their studies and at the same time deprives them of the learning privilege. But even in the curriculum that offers them so many benefits, as they themselves declare, there are issues that need to be resolved, such as inadequate Career Counseling, the use of traditional teaching methods by some teachers that impedes learning, and lack of professional specialization with a focus on the professional arena. It is important that the negative judgments formulated are discussed and studied both in the field of adult education and in educational policy, in order to achieve the best possible results in such an important area as adult correctional education.

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